

AN INNOVATIVE MODEL OF DEVELOPING THE SKILLS OF MAKING ANALOGICAL CONCLUSIONS IN RELATION TO HISTORICAL REALITY IN STUDENTS BASED ON THE DISCIPLINE "PHILOSOPHY AND METHODOLOGY OF HISTORY"

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Abstract: In this article, theoretical-methodological foundations of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality, methodology of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality are studied. Also, an innovative model of developing the skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality in students based on the discipline "Philosophy and Methodology of History" are analyzed.

Key words: historical reality, analogical conclusion, skill, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, corporate, national, historical, technological, competence, innovative model, technological system.

INTRODUCTION. Today, the scientific study of history, an objective approach to it, and the process of interpretation based on specific sources imposes a high responsibility on scientists, researchers, as well as representatives of the educational system, that is, raising a spiritually mature person, education and improving the education system is one of the most important tasks. This educational task is becoming more relevant at the modern stage of the country's development. After all, as President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "The scope of work in the field of education, which plays a decisive role in raising a healthy and well-rounded generation in our country, is increasing more and more." Along with increasing the scope of work in the field of education, the issue of increasing its quality and efficiency remains one of the priority tasks of modern education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Scientific research works on formation of knowledge and skills about historical reality, development of historical consciousness and memory, improvement of historical thinking J.Anderson, D.Blazar, S.A.Henry, K.Halbert, Helen Timperley, Aaron Wilson, Heather Barrar, L.N.Aleksashina , V.V.Barabanov, P.A.Baranov, L.S.Bakhmutova, O.Y.Strelova, M.V.Korotkova, M.T.Studenikin, N.N.Lazukova, Y.M.Persanova, E.Yusupov, J.Tulenov, A.Begmatov, N.Zhorayev, A.Choriyev, O.Gaibullayev .

Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdikulov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriyev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. Jamoldinova in their scientific research found his reflection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. World experience shows that one of the reasons for the rapid development of some countries is that they realized and correctly implemented the organization of national education. Undoubtedly, Uzbekistan has a similar well-thought-out education system. However, the main content of its implementation is the correct implementation of all areas of education, first of all, history education, including the effective use of historical ideals in the pedagogical process, through historical knowledge. It was demanded to expand the historical thinking of the personnel.

The goal of each lesson is, first of all, to form students' conclusions about historical facts and to awaken personal opinion. When evaluating each student, it is necessary to look at the degree to which the subject of the lesson is proven, whether it is based on evidence, based on historical sources. The famous pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasizes the organic interaction and interdependence between different fields and forms of education, and believes that the most important thing in this process is the problem of harmonizing pedagogical influences.

The essence of this problem, which represents one of the most important laws of education, is the following: The pedagogical effectiveness of each means of influencing a person depends on how well thought out, goal-oriented, and effective the other means of influence are. Any influence on a person will be nullified without hundreds of other influences. In this sense, the development of students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality has an educational value, as well as an educational value, which serves as a means of education of national pride.

In all areas of higher education, the use of additional resources is of particular importance as an important didactic tool. This factor is especially important in history education. In particular, historical sources on historical ideals are a reliable source for students to deepen their understanding of a real historical event or phenomenon. This, in turn, requires organizing the educational process on the basis of pedagogical requirements that create certain didactic opportunities.

If the pedagogue ignores this pedagogical requirement, an invisible "psychological barrier" will appear between him and the student. As a result, it has a negative impact on the educational process. For this, the teacher should

use the achievements of psychology and pedagogy, methodological bases of history teaching, new methods, including enriching history education and expanding its didactic possibilities. That is why interactive methods of education are being applied to the educational process in recent years. Therefore, the use of interactive methods in the educational process means the interaction between the teacher and the student, strengthening and activating the relationship. In this sense, history uses the possibility of historical idealism and pedagogical influence of historical heroes, generals, leaders, leaders, politicians, rulers and tsars, representatives of science and mature figures of their time, first of all, education activates the process. After all, interesting education about historical heroes activates the relationship between the teacher and the student. Secondly, the sources that glorify the historical reality enrich didactically the possibility of effective organization of history lessons. At this point, what should be the ways of working with students, their content and form of implementation in order for teachers to use the sources and approaches that reveal the truths about the historical reality? - is a natural question.

One of the important aspects of the activity of a history teacher is the closeness of the teacher to the students, that is, his ability to properly organize pedagogical tactics. After all, in the development of knowledge about historical ideas, like all pedagogical results, the teacher should become the most persuasive person of the student. This approach should be maintained in the process of applying the centuries as a historical source to the historical reality.

A responsible stage of the pedagogical process focused on the development of students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality is the teacher's search for appropriate ways to present the new educational material. In order for the new lesson to be effective and to achieve the teacher's goal in the lesson, this process should include the following: - giving examples of the topic; - it is necessary to analyze the components of the methodological system, first of all, the concepts of historical ideals described in the lesson, and divide them into primary and secondary parts. That is why this process is called the analysis of the textbook text in terms of concepts in didactics. In this case, the teacher determines what new concepts will be learned in this lesson, finds suitable terms for them, and determines ways to work on them. Determines which new concepts are related to the concepts learned in the previous lessons, establishes interconnections, creates a system of guiding questions for students: - evidence of historical ideals, concepts that need to be studied in the history lesson It is presented in a logical sequence and

consistency. Therefore, the teacher, first of all, determines the ways of explaining what comes before and what comes after. At this point, it is necessary to plan in advance the didactic situation in which part (stage) of the lesson (the description of the educational material) and in which form the most basic idea about historical ideals will be presented. It also requires that the place of historical facts be clearly defined in the educational system. The didactic possibilities of using sources related to historical ideals, the method of analyzing this text from a logical and practical point of view, and the fact that students' preparation levels and capabilities are strictly taken into account in the system also increase the didactic possibilities of using sources related to historical ideals. It determines the ways of creating a problem situation in the lesson, implementing interdisciplinary communication, the scope and nature of independent education. At this event, the students' ability to independently find historical ideas similar to the topic and try to make an independent observation about the historical logical connection with this topic creates a basis for a number of didactic conveniences. First, the student independently conducts a unique search for scientific and artistic works related to the historical ideals of the subject, that is, observes the historical fact. Second, the source a student finds may actually be relevant to a particular topic. This factor provides additional didactic comfort to the teacher. Thirdly, this process activates communication between the teacher and the student. In addition, it encourages other students to be active as a unique factor of interest.

By means of the historical method of teaching history and special methods of history education, students will have a clear and correct idea of the past, they will acquire the necessary skills in practice. Exposure to students through auditory, visual, and sensory organs helps them to imagine what historical ideals have done. As a result, their knowledge and skills are deepened and strengthened.

The development of the student's ability to draw analogical conclusions and the formation of historical thinking in history education is a thinking skill and qualification arising from the student's need to know the history of his nation, national statehood (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, analogy, historical use of scientific knowledge methods) is a set. This definition considers the direct goal of history education in the higher education of our country - a systematic approach to the historical process as a holistic phenomenon (past, present, future) by teaching students scientific and artistic works that glorify historical ideals, in which historical It is combined with the development of

general cultural competence through knowledge and instilling the idea of national progress in the hearts and minds of students.

Educational activities aimed at developing the students' ability to make analogical conclusions about historical reality are organized in the following forms according to the scope of students' coverage: 1) activities carried out individually with a specific student; 2) events organized with the participation of certain groups of students; 3) events involving several groups.

"Working in small groups", "Discussion", "Sinkway", "Cluster" technologies are widely used in the system of pedagogical technologies. "Sinkway" is important in the system of interactive methods of didactic process project. The "Sinkwein" method is implemented not by the teacher's activity, but by the student's activity in determining the educational goals and tasks..

Tajriba-sinov ishlarini olib borish jarayonida quyidagi metodlardan foydalanish talabalarda tarixiy voqelikka nisbatan analogik xulosa chiqarish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda samarali ekanligi aniqlandi:

1. The interview method helps students to develop the skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality, to ensure that they think freely and independently about the problem.

2. The question-and-answer method serves to determine students' personal opinions and views on the development of analogical reasoning skills in relation to historical reality. Clear, concise and well-worded questions allow students to think logically.

3. The lecture method is aimed at teaching students about the essence of making analogical conclusions about historical reality, about the factors, conditions and pedagogical possibilities of forming the feeling in question.

4. Explanation method - students are formed to understand the theoretical essence of making an analogical conclusion in relation to historical reality and the social importance of having it, the development of the nation, and its role in ensuring the freedom of the country.

5. The method of practicing in activity (practical exercises) - on the basis of intellectual training, conditions are created for students to develop the skills of drawing analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality.

6. Interactive methods - training students to think freely and independently in relation to historical reality, the skills and competence of organizing a debate, freeing students from standard thinking, as well as collecting diverse ideas on the solution of the discussed problem. allows.

7. Expert evaluation method - helps to ensure impartial, objective, all-round correct evaluation of the activities of event participants (respondents) by peers or by a specially designated group of experts.

8. Hikoya qilish metodi –tarixiy voqelikning ijtimoiy ahamiyati, ana shunday voqelikka asos bo‘luvchi tarixiy shaxslar, bugungi kun qahramonlarining faoliyati xulosa qilinadi. Tushuntirish talabalar tomonidan muammoning mohiyatini to‘g‘ri anglanishiga imkon yaratadi.

9. The method of creating problematic situations provides students with the ability to seriously think about the research problem and the basic concepts that illuminate its essence, and to use the available intellectual opportunities to find a solution to the problem.

10. The method of working with the source - the correct and full understanding of the essence of the concept of historical reality by students, the ability to organize small research activities on the questions and problem situations brought to their attention. helps them to

11. Demonstration method - creates the necessary conditions for the strengthening of the theoretical information acquired by students, the full understanding of the essence of historical reality, and the education of the skills of applying knowledge in practice.

12. The method of practical experiments (research) - thinking logically on the topics brought to the students' attention, putting forward personal opinions, proving and defending their views, convincing their peers, while helping to educate their skills and abilities. creates the necessary conditions for deep understanding of the essence of the problem. Thus, the ability to choose effective forms, methods and means of organizing activities in the complex pedagogical process of developing the skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality in students, and their appropriate and purposeful use gave positive results.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, in order to develop the students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to the historical reality, it is necessary to organize additional and motivational trainings using the free time of the students, to use the opportunities of social networks to become a scientific discussion area, as well as , creating an opportunity to get acquainted with the primary sources that reveal the original truths about historical reality, analyze them, organize discussions based on them, shows a high efficiency in the development of general cultural knowledge and skills.

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